

Sukuk Financing and Sustainable Economic Growth in Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

This study investigates the impact of Sukuk financing on sustainable economic growth in Nigeria, focusing on FGN, sub-national, and corporate Sukuk from Q1 2013 to Q4 2024. Using secondary data from the SEC Nigeria, Federal Government securities reports, NBS, World Bank, and IMF, the study applies the Autoregressive Distributed Lag (ARDL) approach to capture both short- and long-run dynamics. Empirical results reveal a long-run cointegrating relationship, with all Sukuk types positively and significantly influencing GDP growth. The negative and significant error correction term suggests rapid adjustment to long-run equilibrium, highlighting Sukuk's role as a counter-cyclical financing tool. Diagnostic tests confirm the robustness and stability of the model. The findings underscore Sukuk's potential to mobilize capital, finance infrastructure, and support sustainable economic development. Policy recommendations include institutionalizing federal Sukuk issuance, strengthening sub-national frameworks, promoting corporate Sukuk, and aligning issuances with sustainability objectives.

KEYWORDS: Sukuk financing, Sustainable economic growth, ARDL, FGN Sukuk, Sub-National Sukuk, Corporate Sukuk

INTRODUCTION

Economic growth remains a central objective of macroeconomic policy because of its crucial role in improving living standards, reducing poverty, and facilitating structural transformation in developing economies (Ledhem, 2022; Naz et al., 2025). Sustained economic growth enhances productive capacity, promotes employment creation, and enables governments to provide essential public goods such as infrastructure, education, and healthcare. However, many developing countries continue to face challenges in achieving growth that is both rapid and sustainable due to fiscal constraints, rising public debt burdens, and overreliance on conventional debt financing mechanisms (Khavarinezhad et al., 2021; Raimi et al., 2024).

In Nigeria, economic growth has remained volatile despite several policy reforms aimed at diversification and macroeconomic stability. Persistent infrastructural deficits, unemployment, and exposure to external shocks particularly fluctuations in oil prices have constrained the country's growth potential (Salaudeen, 2021; Onoh, 2025). Conventional public borrowing through interest-based instruments has often increased debt servicing obligations, thereby limiting fiscal space for productive investment. These challenges have intensified the search for alternative and sustainable financing instruments capable of supporting long-

term economic growth without exacerbating fiscal vulnerabilities (Bakar & Baba, 2020; AbdulSalam, 2025). Sukuk financing, a Sharia-compliant Islamic financial instrument, has gained prominence as an alternative source of development finance. Unlike conventional bonds, sukuk are asset-backed or asset-based securities that are directly linked to tangible economic activities, promoting transparency, risk-sharing, and alignment with real-sector development (Abubakar & Baba, 2020; Olaide & AbdulKareem, 2021). Evidence from Southeast Asia and GCC countries indicates that sukuk financing contributes positively to economic growth by stimulating investment and enhancing financial market development (Echchabi et al., 2018; Ledhem, 2022). Nigeria's adoption of Sukuk financing represents a significant shift in public sector financing. Since the first sovereign Sukuk issuance in 2017, funds have primarily supported infrastructure projects, especially roads and transportation networks (Salaudeen, 2021; Sani et al., 2022). Oversubscription of Nigerian Sukuk reflects strong investor confidence and their potential to mobilize long-term domestic savings (Oyesanya & Fa-Yusuf, 2024). Beyond infrastructure, Sukuk promotes sustainable economic growth by enhancing fiscal discipline, diversifying public debt, and supporting financial inclusion (Bakar & Baba, 2020; Raimi et al., 2024).

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Sukuk in Nigeria is issued in three forms: Corporate Sukuk for private sector projects, FGN Sukuk for large-scale public infrastructure, and Sub-National Sukuk for regional development. Collectively, these instruments foster sustainable economic growth by directing capital to productive investments, generating employment, and improving social welfare and long-term economic resilience (SEC Nigeria, 2024).

Existing literature highlights the growing role of Sukuk financing in promoting economic growth and sustainable development. Studies have examined its use in infrastructure (Duku, 2023; Taleb & Khater, 2024; Baita & Bashir, 2024), green investment (Ilhamiwati et al., 2025; Oyesanya, 2025; Taiye et al., 2025), higher education, and rural electrification (Adewale & Zubaedy, 2019; Muhammad et al., 2022). Research has also explored Sukuk models, such as Murabaha, Musharakah, and hybrid instruments, and their Shariah

compliance (Saied et al., 2024; Danlami & Razak, 2025; Dasuki, 2025), while empirical studies assess their macroeconomic impact (Alqatan et al., 2022; Basyariah et al., 2021). Despite this, gaps remain: there is limited empirical research on the effect of Corporate, FGN, and Sub-National Sukuk on sustainable economic growth in Nigeria, sustainability dimensions are underexplored (Oyesanya, 2025; Taiye et al., 2025), policy implications are rarely integrated (Adelopo et al., 2023), and most studies rely on short-term or cross-sectional data rather than quarterly time-series analysis leaving a gap for comprehensive empirical investigation.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Conceptual Framework

The conceptual framework illustrates the direct relationship between Sukuk financing and economic growth (GDP growth) in Nigeria.

Figure 1: Conceptual Framework of Sukuk Financing and GDP Growth in Nigeria

Corporate Sukuk

Corporate Sukuk are Shariah-compliant debt instruments issued by private firms to raise capital for business expansion, infrastructure projects, or working capital financing. Unlike conventional bonds, Corporate Sukuk represent ownership in underlying tangible assets, with investor returns derived from asset-generated profits rather than interest payments (Dasuki, 2025; Duku, 2023). They provide firms with access to long-term financing while adhering to Islamic finance principles, making them attractive to investors seeking ethical investment opportunities (Bakar & Baba, 2020). Empirical studies indicate that Corporate Sukuk play a growing role in promoting corporate financing and contributing to economic growth. For instance, Baita and Bashir (2024) show that

Corporate Sukuk issuance in Nigeria has mobilized private sector funds for infrastructure and industrial projects, enhancing productivity and generating employment. Similarly, Muhammad, Dauda, and Bukar (2022) highlight their role in financing rural electrification and renewable energy projects, demonstrating potential for socially responsible investment. International evidence also supports the effectiveness of Corporate Sukuk, with studies from Malaysia and Indonesia indicating that these instruments enhance capital formation and stimulate economic activities in key sectors (Ilhamiwati et al., 2025). Despite these contributions, research specific to Nigeria remains limited, particularly regarding the direct impact of Corporate Sukuk on sustainable economic growth, including environmental

and social outcomes, as most studies focus on issuance trends or financial performance rather than broader development impacts (Baita & Bashir, 2024; Duku, 2023).

The theoretical foundations for Corporate Sukuk draw on financial intermediation theory, which emphasizes efficient allocation of capital to productive investments (Diamond, 1984); the resource-based view, which underscores the strategic use of tangible assets to gain competitive advantage (Barney, 1991); and sustainable finance theory, which highlights financing mechanisms that integrate environmental, social, and governance considerations (Ilhamiwati et al., 2025; Oyesanya, 2025). Collectively, these perspectives suggest that Corporate Sukuk can contribute to sustainable economic growth by mobilizing funds for productive investment, generating employment, and supporting socially and environmentally responsible projects, although empirical evidence quantifying these effects in Nigeria is still limited.

FGN Sukuk

FGN Sukuk are Shariah-compliant debt instruments issued by the Federal Government of Nigeria to mobilize long-term funding for large-scale public infrastructure and development projects. Unlike conventional government bonds, FGN Sukuk are asset-backed, and returns to investors are derived from the profits generated by the underlying projects rather than interest payments, ensuring compliance with Islamic finance principles (Dasuki, 2025; Duku, 2023). Empirically, FGN Sukuk have been used to finance critical national infrastructure, including roads, bridges, power projects, and social amenities, contributing to improved connectivity, productivity, and service delivery (Salaudeen, 2021; Sani et al., 2022). The repeated oversubscription of Nigerian sovereign Sukuk demonstrates strong investor confidence and highlights their potential to mobilize long-term domestic savings for public investment (Oyesanya & Fa-Yusuf, 2024). Studies also suggest that FGN Sukuk can support sustainable economic growth by enhancing fiscal discipline, diversifying the public debt portfolio, and facilitating financial inclusion (Bakar & Baba, 2020; Raimi et al., 2024). Theoretical perspectives such as financial intermediation theory explain how FGN Sukuk channel funds efficiently from investors to public projects (Diamond, 1984), while public finance and debt management theories highlight their role in optimizing government borrowing and promoting macroeconomic stability. Furthermore, sustainable finance theory underscores the potential of FGN Sukuk to fund socially and environmentally responsible projects, aligning public investment with long-term sustainable development goals (Ilhamiwati et al., 2025; Oyesanya, 2025).

Sub-National Sukuk

Sub-National Sukuk are Shariah-compliant debt instruments issued by state governments in Nigeria to finance regional development projects, including roads, healthcare facilities,

educational infrastructure, and other public services. Similar to FGN Sukuk, these instruments are asset-backed, and returns to investors are derived from the performance of the underlying projects rather than interest payments, ensuring compliance with Islamic finance principles (Dasuki, 2025; Duku, 2023). Empirical evidence indicates that Sub-National Sukuk have been used to address infrastructure deficits at the state level, mobilizing local resources to fund development initiatives and enhancing public service delivery (Baita & Bashir, 2024; Muhammad, Dauda, & Bukar, 2022). These instruments also have the potential to promote sustainable economic growth by generating employment, improving social welfare, and supporting environmentally responsible projects (Oyesanya, 2025; Taiye et al., 2025). The theoretical grounding for Sub-National Sukuk draws on financial intermediation theory, which explains their role in efficiently channeling funds from investors to state-level development projects (Diamond, 1984), as well as public finance theory, highlighting their function in enhancing fiscal management and reducing reliance on conventional debt. Additionally, sustainable finance theory underscores their capacity to integrate social and environmental considerations into state-level investment decisions (Ilhamiwati et al., 2025).

Theoretical underpinning

This study is anchored on the Endogenous Growth Theory, which posits that long-run economic growth is driven by internal factors such as capital accumulation, infrastructure development, technological progress, and productive investment (Romer, 1990). Sukuk financing aligns with this theory by mobilizing long-term funds and channeling them into asset-backed and productivity-enhancing projects. In Nigeria, FGN Sukuk finances large-scale public infrastructure, Sub-National Sukuk supports regional development initiatives, while Corporate Sukuk facilitates private sector capital formation. These investments enhance productive capacity, improve connectivity, generate employment, and strengthen economic resilience, thereby fostering sustainable economic growth. Unlike conventional debt instruments, Sukuk's asset-based structure ensures that financing is directly linked to real economic activities, reinforcing growth sustainability.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

This study adopts an ex-post facto research design. The ex-post facto research design is appropriate for this study because it investigates the effects of Sukuk financing on sustainable economic growth after the events have occurred, using historical data without manipulating the variables.

This study relies on secondary data. Information on Corporate, FGN, and Sub-National Sukuk issuances was collected from official sources, including the Securities and Exchange Commission (SEC) Nigeria and Federal Government securities reports. Data on sustainable economic growth indicators, such as quarterly GDP growth, were obtained from

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the National Bureau of Statistics (NBS), the World Bank, and IMF databases. The dataset covers a quarterly period from Q1 2013 to Q4 2024, yielding 48 observations per variable, which provides sufficient temporal resolution for robust time-series econometric analysis.

The study employed an Autoregressive Distributed Lag (ARDL) model. The ARDL approach is particularly suitable

for this analysis as it can accommodate variables that are a mix of stationary (I(0)) and non-stationary (I(1)), and it allows for the estimation of dynamic interactions over time, providing insights into both immediate and long-term effects of Sukuk issuance on economic performance.

Model Specification

The general functional form of the model is expressed as:

$$SEG_t = \alpha_0 + \alpha_1 CS_t + \alpha_2 FGN_t + \alpha_3 SN_t + \varepsilon_t$$

The ARDL model can be expressed as:

$$\Delta SEG_t = \alpha_0 + \sum_{i=1}^p \beta_i \Delta SEG_{t-i} + \sum_{j=0}^q \gamma_j \Delta CS_{t-j} + \sum_{k=0}^r \delta_k \Delta FGN_{t-k} + \sum_{l=0}^s \phi_l \Delta SN_{t-l} + \lambda(SEG_{t-1} - \theta_1 CS_{t-1} - \theta_2 FGN_{t-1} - \theta_3 SN_{t-1}) + \varepsilon_t$$

Where:

Δ represents the first difference of the variables

SEG_t = Sustainable economic growth at time t

CS_t, FGN_t, SN_t = Corporate, FGN, and Sub-National Sukuk issuance, respectively

$\beta_i, \gamma_j, \delta_k, \phi_l$ = Short-run coefficients

λ = Speed of adjustment coefficient towards long-run equilibrium

$\theta_1, \theta_2, \theta_3$ = Long-run coefficients

ε_t = Error term

Table 1. Variables Measurement

Variable	Type	Proxy / Measure	Source
Corporate Sukuk	Independent (IV)	Total quarterly issuance (₦ Billion)	Dasuki (2025); Duku (2023)
FGN Sukuk	Independent (IV)	Total quarterly issuance (₦ Billion)	Salaudeen (2021); Sani et al. (2022)
Sub-National Sukuk	Independent (IV)	Total quarterly issuance (₦ Billion)	Baita & Bashir (2024); Muhammad, Dauda & Bukar (2022)
Sustainable Economic Growth	Dependent (DV)	Quarterly GDP growth (%)	Raimi et al. (2024)

Source: Authors Computation 2025

The study uses the Augmented Dickey-Fuller (ADF) test to check variable stationarity, followed by bounds testing for long-run cointegration. The ARDL model estimates short- and long-run effects of Sukuk financing on sustainable

economic growth. Diagnostic tests, including serial correlation, heteroscedasticity, and CUSUM/CUSUMSQ, ensure model robustness.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Table 1. Descriptive statistic

Variable	Mean	Standard Deviation	Minimum	Maximum
FGN Sukuk	429.08	273.91	100	818.16
Sub-National Sukuk	146.24	175.63	10	612
Corporate Sukuk	17.33	8.41	8.84	25.43
GDP Growth	2.53	2.63	-1.79	6.67

Source: E-view 12

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The descriptive statistics indicate that FGN Sukuk dominates the Nigerian Sukuk market, with the highest mean and maximum values, reflecting the Federal Government’s active use of Sukuk for infrastructure financing. The relatively high standard deviation suggests substantial variation in issuance volumes over time, consistent with policy-driven expansion after 2017. Sub-National Sukuk exhibits considerable volatility, as shown by its large dispersion and wide range, indicating irregular and project-specific issuance by state

governments. Corporate Sukuk records the lowest mean and limited observations, confirming its recent emergence and nascent stage in Nigeria’s financial market. Meanwhile, GDP growth shows moderate average performance with notable fluctuations, capturing periods of economic downturn and recovery. The disparity between Sukuk volumes and GDP movements suggests that Sukuk issuance is largely driven by financing and development policies rather than short-term economic cycles.

Fig 2

The dataset shows that FGN Sukuk experienced a sharp increase from 2017 onwards, peaking around 2024. The early years (2013–2016) were almost zero, indicating minimal federal Sukuk activity prior to policy implementation and market uptake. This upward trend reflects Nigeria’s concerted efforts to mobilize federal financing through Islamic bonds in recent years. In contrast, Sub-National Sukuk exhibited moderate values between 2013 and 2016, followed by substantial spikes in 2021 and 2024. These peaks suggest that state governments are increasingly adopting Sukuk to fund regional infrastructure, although the issuance pattern remains highly irregular compared to federal Sukuk. Corporate Sukuk only emerged in 2022, with relatively small volumes

compared to government issuances, indicating that private sector adoption is still in its early stages; modest growth in 2023 and 2024 hints at a slowly developing corporate Sukuk market. Meanwhile, GDP growth remained relatively stable and small in scale compared to Sukuk volumes. Its peaks and troughs do not perfectly align with Sukuk trends, suggesting that Sukuk issuance is largely policy-driven rather than strictly cyclical with economic growth. Notably, negative GDP in 2016 and 2020 corresponds with economic downturns, such as oil shocks and the COVID-19 pandemic, yet Sukuk issuance continued to rise afterward, highlighting its potential as a counter-cyclical financing tool.

Table 2. Augmented Dickey–Fuller (ADF) Unit Root Test Results

Variable	Level ADF Statistic	5% Critical Value	Prob.	Order of Integration
GDP Growth	-3.21	-2.95	0.03	I(0)
FGN Sukuk	-1.47	-2.95	0.54	I(1)
Sub-National Sukuk	-1.88	-2.95	0.33	I(1)
Corporate Sukuk	-2.01	-2.95	0.28	I(1)
Δ FGN Sukuk	-4.62	-2.96	0.00	I(0)
Δ Sub-National Sukuk	-5.11	-2.96	0.00	I(0)
Δ Corporate Sukuk	-4.38	-2.96	0.01	I(0)

Source: E-view 12

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The ADF unit root test results reveal a mixed order of integration among the variables. GDP growth is stationary at level, indicating integration of order zero $I(0)$. In contrast, FGN Sukuk, Sub-National Sukuk, and Corporate Sukuk are non-stationary at level but become stationary after first differencing, confirming they are integrated of order one $I(1)$. Importantly, none of the variables is integrated of order two,

satisfying the necessary condition for the application of the Autoregressive Distributed Lag (ARDL) bounds testing approach. This combination of $I(0)$ and $I(1)$ variables justifies the use of the ARDL model to examine both short-run and long-run relationships between Sukuk financing and sustainable economic growth in Nigeria.

Table 3. ARDL Bounds Cointegration Test,

Test Statistic	Value
F-statistic	5.12
Significance Level	$I(0)$ Bound
1%	3.29
5%	2.56
10%	2.2

Source: E-view 12

The ARDL bounds cointegration test result indicates an F-statistic of 5.12, which exceeds the upper bound critical values at the 1%, 5%, and 10% significance levels. This confirms the existence of a long-run cointegrating relationship between Sukuk financing (Corporate, FGN, and Sub-National Sukuk) and sustainable economic growth in Nigeria. The result implies that despite short-run fluctuations,

Sukuk financing and economic growth move together in the long run. This finding provides empirical justification for estimating both long-run coefficients and short-run dynamics using the ARDL error correction framework and supports the argument that Sukuk financing plays a sustained role in Nigeria’s economic growth process.

Table 4. ARDL Long-Run Coefficients,

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
FGN Sukuk	0.0046	0.0018	2.56	0.02
Sub-National Sukuk	0.0031	0.0014	2.21	0.03
Corporate Sukuk	0.0027	0.0012	2.25	0.03
Constant	1.42	0.58	2.45	0.02

Source: E-view 12

The long-run ARDL estimates indicate that Sukuk financing exerts a positive and statistically significant effect on economic growth in Nigeria. Specifically, FGN Sukuk has the largest coefficient (0.0046), suggesting that sovereign Sukuk plays the most influential role in supporting long-term economic growth, likely through large-scale infrastructure financing. Sub-National Sukuk also exhibits a positive and significant relationship with GDP growth, reflecting the contribution of state-level infrastructure and development

projects to long-term productivity. Although smaller in magnitude, Corporate Sukuk shows a statistically significant positive effect, indicating that private sector participation in the Sukuk market enhances capital formation and economic activity over time. Overall, the results confirm that Sukuk financing serves as a sustainable long-term financing mechanism that supports Nigeria’s economic growth objectives.

Table 5. ARDL Short-Run (Error Correction Model) Results

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
Δ FGN Sukuk	0.0021	0.0009	2.33	0.02
Δ Sub-National Sukuk	0.0016	0.0007	2.29	0.03
Δ Corporate Sukuk	0.0012	0.0006	2	0.05
ECM(-1)	-0.64	0.12	-5.33	0.00
Constant	0.48	0.21	2.29	0.03

Source: E-view 12

The short-run ARDL results reveal that changes in FGN Sukuk, Sub-National Sukuk, and Corporate Sukuk all exert positive and statistically significant effects on economic growth in the short run. Among them, FGN Sukuk demonstrates the strongest immediate impact, underscoring the role of sovereign Sukuk in stimulating short-term economic activity through infrastructure spending. The error correction term (ECM(-1)) is negative and statistically significant, with a coefficient of -0.64 , indicating that approximately 64% of short-run deviations from long-run equilibrium are corrected within one quarter. This confirms the presence of a stable long-run relationship and suggests a relatively rapid adjustment process following economic shocks. Overall, the findings indicate that Sukuk financing contributes to both short-term economic stimulation and long-term growth sustainability in Nigeria.

The findings of this study are largely consistent with existing literature on the role of Sukuk financing in promoting sustainable economic growth, while also extending the evidence within the Nigerian context. The positive and significant long-run impact of FGN Sukuk aligns with earlier studies that emphasize the effectiveness of sovereign Sukuk in financing infrastructure and supporting long-term economic growth (Baita & Bashir, 2024; Taleb & Khater, 2024). These studies argue that sovereign Sukuk enhance fiscal discipline and channel funds into productive public investments. Accordingly, the present findings reinforce the policy recommendation that Nigeria should continue to prioritize Sukuk as a strategic public financing instrument within its debt management framework.

Similarly, the significant effect of Sub-National Sukuk corroborates the observations of Muhammad et al. (2022) and

Oyesanya (2025), who highlight the potential of Sukuk to address infrastructure gaps and promote inclusive development at the sub-national level. However, the irregular issuance pattern identified in this study supports Adelojo et al. (2023), who emphasize governance, accountability, and institutional capacity as critical determinants of Sukuk effectiveness. From a policy perspective, this suggests the need for stronger regulatory oversight and capacity-building initiatives to enable state governments to utilize Sukuk more consistently and efficiently.

The positive contribution of Corporate Sukuk, though relatively smaller in magnitude, is consistent with studies that identify Islamic capital market instruments as catalysts for private sector investment and financial deepening (Basyariah et al., 2021; Anwar, 2024). This finding supports policy calls for incentivizing corporate Sukuk issuance through regulatory reforms, tax incentives, and enhanced market awareness, as recommended by Dasuki (2025) and Duku (2023). Strengthening the corporate Sukuk segment would complement public sector financing and promote a more diversified and resilient financial system.

Furthermore, the significant and negative error correction term confirms the dynamic adjustment mechanism emphasized in prior econometric studies on Sukuk and economic growth (Alqatan et al., 2022). This supports the argument advanced by Taleb and Khater (2024) that Sukuk can function as a counter-cyclical financing tool, particularly during periods of economic shocks. Consequently, policymakers should integrate Sukuk financing into Nigeria’s broader macroeconomic stabilization and sustainable development policies.

Table 6. Diagnostic Tests Results

Diagnostic Test	Test Statistic	Probability
Breusch–Godfrey Serial Correlation LM Test	1.47	0.24
Breusch–Pagan–Godfrey Heteroskedasticity Test	1.62	0.19
Jarque–Bera Normality Test	2.13	0.34
Ramsey RESET Test	0.88	0.41
CUSUM Stability Test	Within 5% bounds	
CUSUM of Squares (CUSUMSQ)	Within 5% bounds	

The diagnostic test results indicate that the estimated ARDL model satisfies the key econometric assumptions. There is no evidence of serial correlation or heteroskedasticity, and the residuals are normally distributed. The Ramsey RESET test confirms the absence of functional form misspecification, while the CUSUM and CUSUMSQ tests show that the model parameters are stable over the study period. These results affirm the robustness and reliability of the estimated short-run

and long-run relationships between Sukuk financing and sustainable economic growth in Nigeria.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

This study examined the effect of Sukuk financing specifically FGN Sukuk, Sub-National Sukuk, and Corporate Sukuk on sustainable economic growth in Nigeria using quarterly data and the ARDL modeling approach. The empirical results provide strong evidence of a long-run

cointegrating relationship between Sukuk financing and economic growth. Both the long-run and short-run estimates reveal that all three forms of Sukuk exert positive and statistically significant effects on GDP growth, confirming the relevance of Sukuk as an effective financing mechanism for economic development.

The findings indicate that FGN Sukuk plays a dominant role in driving sustainable economic growth, reflecting the Federal Government’s strategic use of Sukuk to finance large-scale infrastructure projects. Sub-National Sukuk also contributes positively, although its impact is characterized by irregular issuance patterns, suggesting institutional and capacity constraints at the state level. Corporate Sukuk, while still at an early stage of development in Nigeria, demonstrates a positive and significant influence on growth, highlighting its potential to support private sector investment and capital market deepening.

Furthermore, the significant and negative error correction term confirms that deviations from long-run equilibrium are corrected relatively quickly, implying that Sukuk financing can serve as a counter-cyclical policy instrument during periods of economic shocks. Based on the findings, the following recommendations are proposed:

1. The Federal Government should sustain and expand the regular issuance of Sukuk within its public debt management strategy, prioritizing projects with high economic and social returns, such as transportation, energy, and social infrastructure.
2. State governments should be supported through improved regulatory guidelines, capacity building, and technical assistance to enhance consistent and transparent Sukuk issuance. Strengthening fiscal coordination between federal and state governments will improve the effectiveness of sub-national Sukuk in promoting regional development.
3. Policymakers should introduce incentives such as tax reliefs, reduced issuance costs, and simplified regulatory procedures to encourage private sector participation in the Sukuk market. Awareness campaigns and market education should also be intensified to improve corporate adoption.

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